

Effectiveness of a Co-management Program With Internal Medicine on Hip Fracture Patients at a Regional Hospital in Northwest Spain. Co-inter-Monf Study

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Abstract

Background

Hip fractures represent a serious public health problem with a high burden of mortality, morbidity, and resource use. Co-management has proven to enhance the clinical outcomes of hip fracture patients hospitalized in various settings.

Aim

This study aims to evaluate whether the previously observed benefits of co-management can be achieved when such a program is implemented in a rural-based district hospital.

Methods

A prospective, single-center observational study was conducted on hip fracture patients hospitalized for hip fracture. Patients were either co-managed by an internal medicine specialist with part-time dedication or not co-managed. The study was conducted in a rural hospital located in Galicia, Northwestern Spain, which serves a population of 45,000.

Results

A total of 207 patients were included in the study, of whom 97 received co-management. The majority of the patients who were co-managed were female (69.1%) and had a median age of 88 years (interquartile range 83–92). The study showed a high burden of comorbidity with a median Charlson index of 6 points, along with high prevalence rates of dementia (46%), functional disability (50%), and chronic anticoagulant therapy (25%). Despite no differences in age, sex, or preadmission cognitive or functional status, the study found lower 30-day postdischarge mortality in co-managed patients (9.3%) compared with the 110 controls (20.0%). The prevalence of osteoporosis treatment, both calcium/vitamin D (87.8% vs. 60.7%) and bisphosphonates/denosumab/teriparatide (42.4% vs. 15.7%), was higher in the co-managed patients at 30 days after discharge. No differences were observed between the two groups in terms of in-hospital mortality and length of stay.

Conclusions

the implementation of internal medicine co-management for hip fracture patients resulted in enhanced outcomes, particularly in the reduction of mortality within 30 days of discharge as well as in the prevalence of osteoporosis treatment.

Introduction

Hip fracture (HF) is a serious public health problem that is associated with a high burden of mortality, morbidity, disability, and resource utilization [1]. Although HF accounts for less than 20% of osteoporotic fractures, its incidence is expected to reach 8 million worldwide by 2050 [3], partly due to aging populations and increased longevity. Literature has shown that the one year mortality rate following HF reaches 20–30% [3], and that only 30–40% of survivors recover their previous functional status [2].

The most common causes of mortality after HF are infectious and vascular diseases [4]. Age, male sex, comorbidity, residence in nursing homes or long-term care facilities, as well as perioperative complications are some of the risk factors for mortality [4]. Recently, a number of studies have shown that medical-surgical co-management is an effective tool for the protection of patients from the consequences of HF, with a reduction in mortality and hospital length of stay (LOS) [5–8]. This model of care has since been incorporated into several practice guidelines [9, 10]. Almost all studies evaluating co-management models in HF have been conducted in academic hospitals, so their feasibility and efficacy in lower complexity systems remain uncertain.

The aim of this study was to assess the impact of internal medicine co-management on the short term mortality, LOS, and osteoporosis treatment of patients hospitalized with HF, compared to a previously published prospective cohort without co-management [11].

Methods

A prospective, single-center, observational study was conducted on patients admitted with HF into a rural 140-bed district hospital between October 2019 and December 2022. In October 2019 our team joined in the Spanish National Hip Fracture Registry (RNFC) [12], and formed a Fracture Liaison Service (FLS) [11]. In November 2021 the current co-management model was initiated. In this model, a part-time dedicated internist visits and manages daily all patients admitted with HF, focusing on perioperative complications and decompensated chronic conditions. Orthopedic surgeons constituted the primary management team in the control cohort, while care was provided symmetrically by surgeons and internists in the co-managed cohort.

Patients older than 75 years admitted to the orthopedic surgery ward with osteoporotic HF were included in the study, regardless whether surgical or medical managed was adopted. Patients with suspected pathological fractures were excluded, as were cases for which informed consent could not be obtained from patients or relatives in presence of dementia or temporary incapacity. Two groups of patients were included in the study: patients admitted since November 2021 who received co-management constituted the treatment group, while patients admitted between October 2019 and November 2021 who received FLS treatment constituted the control group.

Epidemiologic, clinical, and surgical variables were collected on admission and for 30 days after discharge. A detailed history of previous diseases and perioperative complications was only available for

the co-managed group, as these variables were not included in the RNFC, and patients from the historical cohort could not be re-identified from registry data at the time this study was conducted. The study is part of the Spanish National Hip Fracture Registry, approved by the Ethics and Clinical Research Committee of the Hospital Universitario La Paz.

Results are summarized as counts and percentages, as well as medians and interquartile ranges, as these were considered more informative given the expected asymmetry in the distribution of most variables. Pearson's chi-squared and Fisher's exact tests were used to compare categorical variables between the two groups, while the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test was used for quantitative variables. Statistical analyses were performed in R (R Core Team, Vienna, Austria, 2019) using RStudio (RStudio, Boston, MA, 2019). Results are reported according to the STROBE checklist [13].

Results

A total 207 patients were included into the study: 97 co-managed patients and 110 controls managed under the FLS model. Among the 97 co-managed patients (Table 1) most were female (69.1%). Median age was 88 years (interquartile range, *IQR*, 83–92), while median Charlson Comorbidity Index was 6 (*IQR* 5–7) points. Most patients had hypertension (73.2%), while diabetes (22.7%), atrial fibrillation (22.7%), and heart failure (21.6%) were also common. Almost one in four patients was taking oral anticoagulants at the moment of the fracture. A history of disability was present in 50.5% of patients, and 46.4% had some degree of cognitive impairment.

Table 1
Basal characteristics of co-managed patients (n = 97).

Variable	n (%)
Sex, male	30 (30.9)
Age, years; median (IQR)	88 (83–92)
Days until evaluation by the co-management team; median (IQR)	1 (1–2)
Existing conditions	71 (73.2)
- Hypertension	22 (22.7)
- Diabetes	16 (16.5)
- Chronic kidney disease	9 (9.3)
- Coronary artery disease	21 (21.6)
- Heart failure	22 (22.7)
- Atrial fibrillation	11 (11.3)
- Stroke / transient ischemic attack	6 (6.2)
- COPD	9 (9.3)
- Active cancer	7 (7.2)
- Chronic use of alcohol	45 (46.4)
- Cognitive impairment	
Charlson Comorbidity Index; median (IQR)	6 (5–7)
Disability (unable to perform basic ADLs)	49 (50.5)
Nursing home/long-term care facility resident	20 (20.6)

IQR: interquartile range; COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; ADL: activities of daily living; ACEI: angiotensin converting enzyme; ARB: angiotensin receptor blocker; ARNi: angiotensin receptor-neprylisin inhibitor

Variable	n (%)
Previous pharmacological treatment	39 (40.2)
- ACEI/ARB-II/ARNi	4 (4.2)
- Mineralcorticoid receptor blocker	27 (27.8)
- Beta blockers	10 (10.3)
- Thiazide diuretics	19 (19.6)
- Oral antidiabetic agents	4 (4.2)
- Digoxin	24 (24.7)
- Oral anticoagulants	11 (11.3)
o Vitamin K antagonist	13 (13.4)
o Direct action anticoagulant	
IQR: interquartile range; COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; ADL: activities of daily living; ACEI: angiotensin converting enzyme; ARB: angiotensin receptor blocker; ARNi: angiotensin receptor-neprylisin inhibitor	

Patients were evaluated by the co-management team after a median of 1 day (IQR 1–2 days), and were followed up for 5 (IQR 3–7) days until discharge. Sixty (61.9%) patients developed some complication during their admission (Table 2), with a median of 1 complication (IQR 0–2) per patient. The most frequent were delirium (36.1%), acute kidney injury (24.7%), and acute heart failure (17.5%)

Table 2
Complications among co-managed patients (n = 97)

Complications	n (%)
Any complication	60 (61.9)
Count (median, IQR)	1 (0–2)
Delirium	35 (36.1)
Acute kidney injury	24 (24.7)
Acutely decompensated heart failure	17 (17.5)
Pneumonia	10 (10.3)
Water-electrolyte imbalance	6 (6.2)
Urinary tract infection	4 (4.1)
<i>Clostridioides difficile</i> colitis	3 (3.1)
Surgical site infection	1 (1.0)
IQR: interquartile range; COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; ADL: activities of daily living; ACEI: angiotensin converting enzyme; ARB: angiotensin receptor blocker; ARNi: angiotensin receptor-neprylisin inhibitor	

There were no differences in the age, sex, or in the prevalence of physical disability or cognitive impairment between the co-managed patients and the 110 controls (Table 3). The in-hospital mortality rate was similar among both groups (8.2 and 10.1%, $p = 0.846$), as were hospital LOS (5 vs 6 days, $p = 0.192$), and 30-day readmission rates (7.9 vs 10.1%, $p = 0.594$). The cumulative mortality at 30-days postdischarge was significantly lower in co-managed patients (9.3%) than in controls (20.0%, $p = 0.049$). Higher rates of osteoporosis treatment were observed 30 days after discharge in co-managed patients.

Table 3
Outcomes in co-managed (n = 97) and non-co-managed patients (n = 110) .

Variable	CM, n (%)	Controls, n (%)	P
Sex, male	30 (30.9)	23 (20.9)	0.137
Age, years; median (IQR)	88 (83–92)	87 (84–92)	0.886
Cognitive impairment	45 (46.4)	47 (55.3)*	0.294
Disability	49 (50.5)	41 (37.6)**	0.085
In-hospital mortality	8 (8.2)	11 (10.0)	0.846
30-day mortality	9 (9.3)	22 (20.0)	0.049
Length of stay, days; median (IQR)	6 (4–8)	5 (4–8)	0.192
Readmission at 30 days	7 (7.9)	10 (10.1)	0.594
Calcium/vitamin D at 30 days	87 (87.8)	54 (60.7)	< 0.001
Bisphosphonate, denosumab or teriparatide at 30 days	42 (42.4)	14 (15.7)	< 0.001
CM: co-management; IQR: interquartile range;			
*Data missing for 25/110 patients			
**Data missing for 1/110 patients			

Discussion

Hip fractures are a frequent hospitalization cause in elderly people, involving a large morbidity and mortality burden. Surgical treatment is usually needed, although a minority of cases are managed conservatively [14, 15]. Osteosynthesis surgery for HF is a critical event that can entail perioperative complications including decompensation of chronic conditions; because of this, medical co-management of patients with HF has gained popularity in the last years [9, 10].

Patients with HF have a high mortality risk compared with the general population [2], that can be as high as five times that of patients without HF [16]. Mortality rates are especially high immediately after the fracture and during the first month, and remain increased until 10 years after the event [16]. Male sex, multimorbidity, and nursing home or long-care term facility residence have been linked to higher mortality rates [1, 16]. In hospital mortality was higher among our patients than in other studies [3, 5, 6, 8, 17], which could be explained partially since our sample comprises mostly the oldest old, with a median age of 88 years. As in other experiences [5], in-hospital mortality was not modified by the implementation of co-management, but medium-term mortality was reduced by 53% compared to patients not co-managed.

Several studies have shown that medical co-management reduces the mean LOS [5, 6, 8] in patients with HF; this was not observed in our sample, probably because the basal LOS was altogether low compared

with an average of 10 to 15 days in previous studies in Spain [3, 14, 15]. Shortening the hospital admissions in these patients is important to avoid complications derived from prolonged hospitalization, such as delirium or disuse atrophy. In our institution this is achieved due to a high proportion of early operated patients [11], and early intervention of the co-management team (median delay from admission of one day). This in turn entails a high workload for the internal medicine department, considering a median of 5 days of follow-up per patient, slightly less than has been reported elsewhere [18]. Although both the length of stay and the follow up duration are shorter than in other series, this did not associate a higher readmission in our study [5, 6, 8].

During their admission, 61.9% of our patients developed at least one complication. This is higher than the 30–40% incidence described in the literature [3–17], but since hard outcomes were not worse, this could be a relative overreporting that might derive from the prospective design and the more thorough documentation of complications detected when medical specialists participate in the care continuum [19]. Among these complications, delirium was the most incident, as observed in previous experiences [17].

Osteoporotic bone fractures represent one of the main risk factors for second fractures, particularly during the first year [1]. Osteoporosis treatment has been proved to cost effectively reduce both mortality and the risk of new fractures [7]. Although HF usually induces clinicians to initiate these therapies [7, 20], data from the Spanish National Hip Fracture Registry show that only 41% of patients receive them 30 days after a HF event. In our series, 87.8% of the co-managed patients were under osteoporosis treatment by that time, with a higher proportion than not co-managed patients even though they were included in a FLS [11].

Among the primary limitations of our study is its observational nature, hindering the establishment of causal relationships, in conjunction with insufficient patient history and complications data in the control group. Conversely, this represents to our knowledge the first documented experience of HF co-management in a district hospital within a rural context, highlighting that some of the benefits previously observed at academic institutions can indeed be extended to patients in this setting.

Conclusions

Internal Medicine Co-management of patients with osteoporotic hip fracture was associated with decreased mid-term mortality and increased osteoporosis treatment in a rural-based district hospital.

Declarations

Author Contribution

A. R. A. included patients and elaborated introduction. J. L. C. prepared discussion and tables. J. C. C. elaborated material and methods and wrote up results. V. Q. V. elaborated material and methods and

wrote up results. A. M. L. prepared the database and performed the statistical analysis. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

Conflict of interest.

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest with respect to the present study.

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